

Transcription of Interview with Interview 5 Interview 5

*for Shane Murphy
November 2020*

Shane: So starting the first question, rather broadly, is, what are your views on the National Health Insurance?

Interview 5: Alright. My view is, I don't know whether it will work for us, or it won't work for us. But my view is what the government is trying to do, to say, we need to have equality, as all South African citizens, **in spite [of]** our backgrounds and our economy status. But, for me, it's something that will work, or it's a model that have worked in the developed countries. So I'm not so sure how is it going to work in a country like South Africa.

Shane: And why would you say you have those concerns within the South African setting?

Interview 5: My concern is about the type of infrastructures that we have, in the facilities that we have, especially in the rural areas, where, even now, when we're talking about inception of NHI, but you still find facilities, even here in Gauteng, facilities that doesn't meet the standard of what will say it is an ideal facility.

Shane: Okay. So you would say, largely, the standards of the public sector, and not meeting, as put forward by the ideal clinic standards?

Interview 5: Yes.

Shane: Okay. And what are your views around the strategic purchasing of how the NHI will form a board that then, functions independently, and purchases service from the private and public sector?

Interview 5: I think, in that route of purchasing services from the private sector, that one can help, or can assist, in terms of improving the services for the public, as a whole. But the issue will be, how do we do that? What processes are we going to follow, to purchase those services? I think that is my main concern, **in saying** that route that we will follow, in terms of purchasing those services. If we are saying, now we need to have the universalism, in terms of oncology, or whatever, are we not going to end up now, having more collusion, to say, people will go **[..]**, they won't be working in the stage, or in the government sector, they will be at their private sector, so that they can get more money. So that's my concern.

Shane: And you think that the governance over the funding - am I understanding correctly? - to say that you have some concerns about that?

Interview 5: Yes, I think, ja, that's the correct way to.. governance, in terms of the funding; how are we going to be governing that?

Shane: Okay. And why do you, in particular, have concerns around the governance of the funding?

Interview 5: When you look what is really happening in terms of government, there are so many corruptions, so many things, every day, when you listen to the news, it's all about corruption, people

who are enriching themselves; like now, if you can look into the PPE issues. So it's something that I don't know how do we prevent it, if it happened also during this covid time, when we're supposed to considerate for our people, what will then happen under normal circumstances? People will just keep on enriching themselves.

Shane: Yes. And one of the models that they want to use, is the capitation, or per capita payment. Do you have any views on that?

Interview 5: Maybe I'm not so sure, in terms of capita payments, how is it supposed to work. So I don't know, I don't want to comment on something that I'm not so sure of what the per capita payment, how is it going to work, or what.

[05:12]

Shane: So, classically, we have a, out-of-pocket payment, or medical aid payment, and so there's a switch from that, more on the person using the service, that has to pay, and has the excess loss, or expenditure on health, and what they want to do is, say, okay, you, as a general practitioner, you service this 10,000 population, and we give you a number of R150 per person, whether they use the substance or not; with the idea of trying to cut costs down, doctors won't do unnecessary investigations or tests, it's just to control costs and expenditure.

Interview 5: On my side, I don't think it will work a hundred percent, if like now, I'm just given, to say, 10,000 or maybe 5,000 people in the catchment area, whether they've accessed the service or not, I'm still going to be paid; how are we saving the cost, then, even if people, they didn't access the service, but the service provider is still being paid. So there's no cost saving in that model, unless, if they were saying, yes, you will be servicing this area, but you will be paid depending on the people who have come to access service; then that was much more understandable in terms of cost saving.

So that model is not cost saving at all, it will even open more doors of corruption; because I can say, in this area, or people that have registered in this area, I've registered 20,000, when I know, very well, that people, maybe, at that side it's only 2,000; so we can inflate the numbers. So we can have [...] from the Stats SA, to say, in this area this is **one, two, three**, but you know how we can do so. For me, that model won't work; it will open more doors for corruption.

Shane: Yes. Off the top of your head, do you have any idea that would work? Or what would be the best way to..?

Interview 5: **No, whatever** the models that we are currently using now, those who are on medical aid, let them pay, using their medical aid, let them access services where they want to access the service, let us not enforce our ideas that are working in other countries, to the citizens, or to South African society. Because what is working in Europe, what is working in England, what is working wherever, it will not work here in this South Africa, in this community, where **people** have got lot of things.

Imagine now, when you were used to go to the private hospital services, you get them in five minutes time; now you need to come to Hillbrow, where you will have to stay in a queue for ten hours, or whatever. So let's just try and better the services in the private (**public?**) sector, and then not like now,

saying we are joining everything, so that you only can access.. For me, that won't work. So let's just leave the system the way they are, and then better the public sector.

Shane: Okay. And with regards to, in your personal engagement with the NHI policy development input and feedback, have you had much of that?

Interview 5: I didn't attend the sessions that were organised for the public; I didn't have that time to go and attend those sessions. Yes, I knew about them, that they were engaging the stakeholders, even here at UJ, but I didn't attend.

Shane: Okay. And were there many activities that the government did try to reach out? Or just those that you've mentioned?

Interview 5: If I can say, it's.. ja, I cannot say many or less, mostly for the community to understand, is when you hear it on television. But not so many **Magutlas** or whatever, **Mbiso**, that were heard along this, to say, now we are educating people on what is this all about. It's only when, now, they have to pass the Bill, they will call certain sectors and then discuss it with them. But in terms of public engagement, I won't say much was done to engage the public.

[10:29]

Shane: Okay. And in your managerial position, how do you get most of your information on the NHI? Are there regular updates, or progress reports, or is it largely mainstream media?

Interview 5: No; from the National Department of Health, they do send communications.

Shane: Okay. Do you think that the NHI is progressing, and going ahead adequately?

Interview 5: No.

Shane: Why do you say that?

Interview 5: I will still go back to the issue, the infrastructure, and then also the issue of also the inspection. Remember, when it comes to this National Health Insurance, we were informed that the Office of Health Compliance Standards, they will do the inspections so that they can certify the facilities. So the tool has been on trial, since.. it's only then, now, been only for the primary healthcare facility, where it was approved this year. So we are still much more far to reach, to say, now this facility, in terms of the inspections that were conducted, by the Office of Health Compliance Standards; they **need** their requirement to be 35 as an National Health Insurance facilities. So I think, for me, we are still far, because even the tools for the hospitals, to assess if they are ready for NHI, it is not yet approved; it's still on the trial, on the draft.

Shane: Okay. And that actually speaks a lot to my next question, that was, your perception about the readiness of the overall public service. And as far as I can understand, from you, is that they're not ready, and the systems to assess and improve, haven't been followed appropriately. Is that correct?

Interview 5: Yes, that's what I can say, yes. Because when we are talking about the facilities that can do whatever, you need to have good infrastructure, you need to have adequate staff; I think we always hear, even in the media, the complaints that we get, to say, we don't have adequate staff. Yes, in terms of medicine, at least we do have medicine, is not where we will say we don't have a lot of medicine; then it also need good administrative processes. So ja, that's what I can say.

Shane: And what would you say, what would need to happen, sort of solutions to make the NHI be implemented and run effectively?

Interview 5: What need to happen, we need to have the good infrastructure, adequate staffing, we need to have adequate supplies, good administratives, and then we also need to have the policies, protocols, guidelines, in place; and then involve all the stakeholders that need to be involved, so that we all have the same understanding about what is the government expecting from us, and then what is the government trying to achieve, by giving this NHI to all its citizens, by implementing this NHI.

Shane: And as it stands, you would say, that that's not working at the moment, and not getting everyone's buy-in and engagement?

Interview 5: No. For me, to be realistic, it's not getting that whatever; it's only when, probably, if they have set a goal to say, by 2020 or 2021, and then when they are reviewing, to say, how far are we, is only the time when you will hear people talking about, then, NHI. But even now, if you can go, I know there's covid on whatever, when last did you hear about NHI in the media?

[15:10]

Shane: Ja, not at all, ja.

Interview 5: Not at all. So are we ready? But if then, when they are reviewing their APPs, to review their goals, to say, oh by the way, by this time, we are supposed to do one, two, three, it's only then, you will hear them going back, to say, ja, we are ready. But are ready in Papers, but at a ground level, we are not ready.

Shane: Why do you think there's such a disconnect between the Papers and the ground level?

Interview 5: Yoh!

Shane: Do you think the policy makers are not necessarily working on the ground level, and just set out rules but they don't know the practicalities?

Interview 5: I think they know the practicality, but you know, when you have set goals and.. I think, for me, it's more political; because if you have set goal, to say, by this.. as a government, you will then try, and then.. because you have a mandate, isn't it?

Shane: Ja.

Interview 5: To say, by this and that, we want to have achieved this. And then at the end of the day, especially when you are campaigning or whatever, then you will start to say, no, we have reached these,

we are working on this process; for example, maybe you will say, we have built ten hospitals, from this period to this period; but what about all these ones that are existing, that are not well-maintained? What about the areas where people still need to travel about a hundred kilometres, about whatever, to access.. So all those kind of things, we are not saying it. We will only focus, to say, no, in the period of ten years or whatever, we have managed to build, one, two, three, one, two, three, but even then, you go into those facilities that have been built, they don't comply to the standards.

Shane: Hmh!

Interview 5: But in actual fact, when we report, we won't be reporting all the bad things or all these other.. like the way I'm talking now, we don't say all those things. So obviously, if the MEC want their report, whatever, we will try and paint as if everything is going good, so that it mustn't be seen as if we are failing. So maybe that's where there's this discrepancy between the policies, the whatever, because we will want to be seen, or to portray, as if everything is working good; whereas in reality, we know that it is not working good.

Shane: So I know, in terms of performance assessments, that's probably a big risk factor, why you would portray it as working.. or not as working, when you don't really feel that it is. Do you think that that's an obstruction, and a lack of communication and teamwork, from your seniors, that would support you, and say, what are our challenges? How can we go..?

Interview 5: Ja, I will agree that, to say, mostly, yes, it can be teamwork, and even lack of support; because what I think, what we normally focus on, it's more of did we reach that indicator? I think, for me, it's to more of bridging the.. how was the indicator reached? Or even if I can present something to say, on this indicator, we are doing this; as long as it [...] the target, it's 50%, and I present 55[%]; there will be no questions to say, how did you [...], how did you do whatever. As long as you are presenting, to say, I'm at 55%, when the target was 50[%]. Only when, if it.. say for example, let me give you a practical example; [...] clinic **would** be ideal, né?

Shane: Ja.

Interview 5: The facilities should be ideal; but in actual fact, you know that that facility's not ideal. Now, if you didn't reach the target, you will be asked, why is this facility, it didn't reach the target? Knowing very well - I don't know if you are familiar - you have got park-home, which, in terms of their ideal standard, that clinic will never reach the ideal status if it is a park-home, because it doesn't have adequate whatever. But you will be asked to say, why didn't it reach? At the end of the day, people will end up even saying, we do have this, this and that, so that they score the points.

Shane: Sjoe!

Interview 5: Ja, so that's why I'm saying that something is not right.

[20:02]

Shane: Mr Interview 5, you've provided me with a lot of information. At the outset, I forgot to ask, what is your current role, and employment title?

Interview 5: I am the Deputy Director Quality Assurance. I'm the one who need to ensure that everything in the facilities are done according to the standards and norms.

Shane: Ja, you know; you're the best person to speak to about that. Okay, that's the questions from my side; the last one is just rather broadly, is there any other view or thought, that you would like to express on the NHI, or the process, or your feelings, or so?

Interview 5: Another view that I would like to express is, let's engage stakeholders, and then let's also be practical, I think practicality, it's what is most needed. We cannot say all facilities, at a go, they will be NHI ready and whatever, when we know that in reality, that is not true. I think if we can just target, to say, let's say, for City of Johannesburg, facility one, two, three, or the service providers **wherever**, that we can make them ready to be NHI, and then we work towards improving others, so that they can also be part of this NHI. But this one of saying, at a go, everything will be ready, I think that one, it won't be feasible. So we just need to work on more processes, on the engagement of stakeholders, on the engagement of the community, to say, what is their viewpoint on understanding these, engaging also the service providers, these private sectors, to say, how are we going to work together to improve the services in the public sector?

Shane: Perfect. That's all from my side. Thanks so much for your time, you've really given me some useful information.

Interview 5: Ja, I know it [...] planning, or it can be viewed as a negative comment or whatever, but I felt like, let me just be honest with how I feel; rather than also to sugar-coat and say, ja, this is working, this is going to work, or whatever.

Shane: No, your input is invaluable; because the outcome of our research, is to identify shortcomings. Obviously, anonymise the info, and then just put the.. like, what is the feeling of the managers around it; and so, by that, identify, and then working challenges, and having discussions with the stakeholders, as you say. So it's been really great, ja.

Interview 5: Okay.

Shane: Okay, thanks so much for your time.

Interview 5: You're welcome, thank you.

Shane: Thanks. Bye.

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